

THE EFFECT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION AT SMA NEGERI 1 NABIRE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of transformational leadership and organizational culture on teacher performance through job satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. The research employed a quantitative approach with an associative research design. The population consisted of all teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire totaling 56 respondents, who were also used as the research sample. Data were collected through a questionnaire using a Likert scale and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with the assistance of SmartPLS software. The results indicate that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on both job satisfaction and teacher performance, while organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction but does not directly affect teacher performance. Job satisfaction is found to have a positive and significant effect on teacher performance and acts as a mediating variable in the research model. Job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance and fully mediates the relationship between organizational culture and teacher performance. These findings suggest that improving teacher performance is influenced not only by leadership and organizational culture but also by the level of teachers' job satisfaction. Therefore, strengthening transformational leadership and fostering an organizational culture that enhances teachers' job satisfaction are important strategies for improving teacher performance, particularly in schools located in areas with limited resources.

Keywords: *transformational leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, teacher performance.*

INTRODUCTION

National development aims to realize a just and prosperous society, both materially and spiritually, based on the principles of Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution (Suarmanayasa, 2021). Education is one of the most important aspects of national development. Education is a fundamental factor in national development aimed at improving the quality of human resources. In this era work environment, human resources play an important role as the driving force and key determinant in achieving organizational goals (Anjeli & Heryanda, 2025). Human resources are one of the organizational resources that constitute the core of competitive advantage and cannot easily be imitated by other organizations (Widiana & Heryanda, 2023). In this context, senior high schools (SMA) as formal secondary education institutions play an important role in shaping the character and competencies of the younger generation. A quality learning process is not only determined by the curriculum but also largely depends on teachers' performance as the primary implementers of education within educational institutions. Teachers who demonstrate strong performance are able to create a conducive, interactive, and meaningful learning environment, thereby significantly improving students' learning outcomes (Prihono et al., 2022). Teacher performance in carrying out their duties does not operate independently; rather, it is influenced by various internal and external factors. Previous studies indicate that school leadership and organizational culture have a significant positive influence on teacher performance, both directly and indirectly through psychological variables such as motivation and job satisfaction. This finding is supported by the research of Christin et

al. (2023), which revealed that leadership has a positive effect of 0.234 on teacher performance, while organizational culture has a stronger influence of 0.483 on employee performance. Further analysis also shows a positive influence of leadership (0.182) and organizational culture (0.395) on teacher performance, although work motivation in the study shows a negative effect of -0.46. These findings confirm that leadership, organizational culture, and job satisfaction are important variables in explaining variations in teacher performance.

Leadership in the field of education plays an important role in determining the direction, climate, and quality of learning in schools. Transformational leadership is characterized by a leader’s ability to demonstrate charisma, provide inspirational motivation, develop a clear vision, and pay attention to individual needs, thereby creating a conducive work environment and continuously encouraging teacher performance (Widyastuti et al., 2024; Kaya, 2024). In addition, a strong organizational culture reflects values and norms that promote cooperation, open communication, and a healthy work atmosphere, which can enhance job satisfaction and teacher performance (Schein, 2010). Job satisfaction itself represents a psychological condition that reflects positive feelings toward one's work, where teachers who experience higher levels of satisfaction tend to demonstrate stronger motivation and more optimal performance. In an increasingly dynamic work environment, competition among employees has become more intense. Therefore, it is important for every individual to possess competencies and skills that align with the demands of the job (Pratama & Suarmanayasa, 2025).

This complex and multidimensional condition is also evident at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire, Nabire Regency, Papua. As a newly established public high school located in a relatively remote geographical area, SMA Negeri 1 Nabire faces various challenges in managing the educational process. Currently, the school has approximately 61 teachers and 1,223 students. The relatively limited number of teachers compared to the high administrative and academic workload creates considerable work pressure. In addition, the school’s geographical location, which is far from the city center, along with limited educational facilities, further exacerbates these challenges. One indicator that reflects teachers’ working conditions is their attendance rate. This issue highlights ongoing concerns regarding leadership and organizational culture in the field of education, particularly in remote regions such as Nabire Regency, Papua. Based on data collected from the Nabire Regency Education Office, several public schools continue to face issues related to consistent teacher absenteeism and limited participation in professional training programs. Internal school data also indicate that during the period from November to May 2025, the teacher attendance rate showed a declining trend. Table 1.1 below illustrates the average teacher attendance during this period.

Table 1. Percentage of Teacher Attendance at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire

Month	Number of Working Days	Average Days Attended per Teacher	Percentage
November	21	52	85.2%
December	20	51	82.8%
January	20	54	88.5%
February	19	50	83.6%
March	22	55	85.2%
April	21	53	85.9%

(Source: Processed Data, 2025)

The trend of teacher attendance still shows monthly fluctuations, with the average attendance rate ranging between 82% and 88%. This condition indicates the presence of underlying issues related to teachers’ motivation and job satisfaction that need to be addressed promptly. If not properly managed, the decline in teacher performance may have long-term implications for the quality of education in remote areas such as Nabire, Papua. In terms of the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process, this phenomenon highlights the need to further examine the factors that influence teachers’ motivation and job satisfaction, particularly those related to the principal’s leadership and the organizational culture within the school environment.

The principal's leadership is a key element in creating a healthy and productive work climate. A leadership style that is able to inspire and motivate teachers in carrying out their duties is transformational leadership, which emphasizes vision, idealized influence, and the empowerment of organizational members (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Principals who adopt a transformational leadership style tend to provide individualized attention, intellectual stimulation, and foster positive emotional relationships with teachers. This leadership style has been proven effective in increasing teachers' loyalty, motivation, and job satisfaction (Gultom, 2021).

On the other hand, organizational culture also plays a vital role in shaping teachers' attitudes and work behavior. Organizational culture refers to a system of values, beliefs, and norms that are formed and maintained within an institution, which indirectly determines how individuals interact and perform their work (Sinambela, 2019). In the school environment, organizational culture includes aspects such as communication styles, reward systems, a collective work climate, and the enforcement of discipline. A strong and positive organizational culture has been proven to enhance social cohesion, a sense of belonging, and teachers' job satisfaction (Simamora, 2021).

Various studies have shown that both transformational leadership and organizational culture have a significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction. However, most of these studies focus on schools located in urban areas with adequate facilities and relatively stable management support. In fact, education in 3T regions (Frontier, Remote, and Underdeveloped areas) has different characteristics and challenges, such as limited infrastructure, restricted access, and unequal distribution and competence of teaching staff (Valmay et al., 2024). In Papua in particular, the education sector also faces serious issues, including a high rate of teacher absenteeism influenced by leadership factors, socio-cultural conditions, and limited educational facilities (UNICEF, 2024). This fact indicates that empirical studies examining the influence of leadership and organizational culture on teachers' job satisfaction in remote areas, especially in Papua, remain very limited. Therefore, this study is important to fill this research gap, particularly in understanding the dynamics occurring at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire, Nabire Regency.

Considering the complexity of the challenges faced by SMA Negeri 1 Nabire, this research becomes highly relevant. The declining trend in teacher attendance indicates potential problems related to teachers' motivation and work enthusiasm, which may affect the quality of the learning process and students' academic achievement. One factor that needs to be further evaluated is the extent to which the principal's leadership and the prevailing organizational culture are able to create a supportive and satisfying work environment for teachers. However, empirical studies examining the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational culture, and teachers' job satisfaction remain limited, particularly in 3T regions (Frontier, Remote, and Underdeveloped areas) such as Papua. Therefore, this study aims to examine "The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance through Job Satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire, Nabire, Papua." By investigating the interaction between these aspects, this research is expected to provide academic contributions to the improvement of educational quality in remote areas.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Leadership is an activity of guiding a group in order to achieve the goals of the group, namely shared objectives (Ardani & Heryanda, 2025). Transformational leadership is a leadership style that emphasizes a leader's ability to inspire, motivate, and develop individual potential in order to achieve organizational goals and promote positive change. Leadership is a crucial figure that plays a significant role and has a strong influence on performance (Dwi & Suarmanayasa, 2022). This concept was first introduced by Burns (1978) and later developed by Bass and Avolio (2004), who emphasized that transformational leaders not only focus on achieving organizational goals but also encourage the professional growth of subordinates through an inspiring vision and attention to individual needs (Bass & Riggio, 2006). In the context of education, transformational leadership is capable of creating an innovative, collaborative, and supportive work environment that enhances teacher performance (Joen et al., 2022;

Siahaan et al., 2023). The variable of transformational leadership is measured using the indicators of idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, as proposed by Bass and Avolio (2004).

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a system of values, norms, beliefs, and assumptions shared by members of an organization that serve as guidelines for behavior and interaction in achieving organizational goals. Organizational culture reflects the characteristics of an organization that are formed through work habits, value systems, and patterns of relationships among organizational members (Pasla, 2023). The value system within organizational culture can serve as a behavioral guideline for individuals and is oriented toward achieving the predetermined goals or work standards (Semarandani & Suarmanayasa, 2025). According to Schein, as cited in Suprpto and Hermaningsih (2020), organizational culture functions as a guide for the behavior of organizational members in carrying out their daily activities. In the context of schools, a strong and positive organizational culture can encourage cooperation, increase work motivation, and strengthen teacher performance. The organizational culture variable is measured using the indicators of innovation and risk-taking, attention to detail, outcome orientation, people orientation, team orientation, aggressiveness, and stability, as proposed by Robbins and Judge (2017).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive emotional state that arises from an individual's evaluation of their job and the work experiences encountered within an organization. Robbins and Judge (2017) state that job satisfaction reflects an individual's positive feelings toward their job, which result from an evaluation of the characteristics of that job. Job satisfaction is a universal attitude of employees toward their work, reflecting a comparison between the rewards they receive and the rewards they believe they deserve (Efendy & Suarmanayasa, 2021). In the educational environment, teachers' job satisfaction is very important because it can enhance teachers' motivation, loyalty, and performance in carrying out their professional duties (Hasibuan, 2016). Job satisfaction is an interesting and important issue because it has been proven to benefit individuals, organizations, and society. When individuals feel satisfied with their jobs, they tend to strive to improve their quality of life (Pradnyana & Suarmanayasa, 2025). Job satisfaction is believed to be influenced not only by working conditions (Metariani & Heryanda, 2022). The theory of job satisfaction is also explained through Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which distinguishes between motivator factors and hygiene factors in influencing an individual's job satisfaction (Herzberg, 1966 in Zajda, 2023). The job satisfaction variable is measured using indicators such as satisfaction with the work itself, satisfaction with salary, satisfaction with coworkers, satisfaction with supervision or superiors, and satisfaction with career development opportunities, as proposed by Luthans (2011) and Gibson et al. (2012).

METHOD

This study employs an associative quantitative approach to examine the relationships and effects among transformational leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, and teacher performance. This approach allows for an objective analysis of causal relationships among variables through the processing of numerical data obtained from questionnaires and analyzed using inferential statistical techniques. The research design used is causal-comparative, which aims to determine the influence of one variable on another (Sugiyono, 2016). The research population consists of all permanent and honorary teachers actively teaching at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire during the even semester of the 2024/2025 academic year, totaling 61 individuals. Therefore, the entire population was used as the research sample. Data were collected through questionnaires based on a five-point Likert scale, interviews, and documentation to obtain both quantitative and contextual information related to the research variables (Ghozali, 2018; Sugiyono, 2019). The transformational leadership variable was measured using the indicators of idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Bass & Riggio, 2006). The

organizational culture variable was measured using indicators of innovation, attention to detail, outcome orientation, and concern for employees (Pasla, 2023). The job satisfaction variable was measured using indicators of the work itself, salary, promotion, supervision, coworkers, and working conditions (Robbins & Judge, 2017). Meanwhile, teacher performance was measured using indicators of timeliness in task completion, conformity with plans, attendance, and team collaboration (Kasmir, 2016). Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with the assistance of SmartPLS 4.1 software, as this method is suitable for predictive research with relatively small sample sizes and does not require normally distributed data (Hair et al., 2017). The analysis was carried out through two main stages. The first stage was the evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) to assess the validity and reliability of the indicators using loading factor values, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha, and Composite Reliability. The second stage was the evaluation of the structural model (inner model) to examine the relationships among variables through path coefficients, t-statistics, and p-values using the bootstrapping procedure. In addition, the quality of the model was evaluated using R-square (R^2), Q-square (Q^2), effect size (f^2), and Goodness of Fit (GoF). Hypothesis testing included both direct effects among variables and indirect effects through job satisfaction as a mediating variable, which were analyzed using the Variance Accounted For (VAF) approach to determine whether the mediation effect was full or partial (Hair et al., 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

Data Description

This study was conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire by involving 56 teachers as respondents to describe respondent characteristics and the distribution of responses related to the variables of transformational leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, and teacher performance. The measurement used a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, where values closer to 1 indicate a more positive perception of the statements provided. Based on the respondents' characteristics, the majority of teachers were female, totaling 34 individuals (60.7%), while 22 respondents (39.3%) were male. In terms of age, most respondents were in the 21–30 year age group (48.2%), followed by those aged 31–40 years (28.6%), indicating that the teaching staff is largely composed of individuals in their productive age. Regarding educational background, the majority of teachers hold a Bachelor's degree (S1) at 78.6%, while 21.4% have completed a Master's degree (S2). In terms of work experience, most respondents have 1–5 years of teaching experience (55.4%), followed by 6–10 years (32.1%), indicating that the teaching workforce in the school is dominated by relatively early-career teachers while still supported by more experienced educators. The results of the descriptive analysis indicate that respondents' perceptions of all research variables fall within the positive to very high categories. The transformational leadership variable is rated very highly, as all respondents provided responses of *agree* and *strongly agree*, indicating that the principal is able to provide motivation, serve as a role model, encourage creative thinking, and show attention to teachers. The organizational culture variable is also categorized as high, with a dominance of *agree* responses on indicators such as innovation, attention to detail, outcome orientation, and concern for employees, although a small number of respondents expressed neutral opinions regarding work feedback. Meanwhile, teachers' job satisfaction is categorized as very high, particularly in aspects related to leadership supervision and promotion policies. However, the salary indicator shows several neutral responses, suggesting that compensation remains an aspect requiring attention. For the teacher performance variable, the analysis results indicate a high category, with the majority of respondents stating that they are able to perform their duties well. Nevertheless, a few respondents expressed neutral views regarding punctuality and discipline. Overall, the conditions of leadership, organizational culture, and job satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire are considered supportive of achieving optimal teacher performance.

Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS)

Measurement Model Evaluation (Outer Model)

The measurement model evaluation was conducted to ensure that the instruments used in this study (the questionnaire) are both valid and reliable. This analysis includes tests of convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

Picture 1. Measurement Evaluation (Outer Model)
(Source: Processed Data, 2026)

The measurement model (outer model) evaluation was conducted to assess the adequacy of the indicators in representing the latent constructs used in this study. The outer model testing includes the assessment of the validity and reliability of the indicators to ensure that the research instruments are capable of measuring each variable accurately and consistently. The initial evaluation results, as presented in Figure 1, indicate that, in general, the indicators used have met the required measurement criteria. Therefore, the measurement model is considered appropriate to proceed to the structural model testing stage.

Table 2. Summary of Outer Model Evaluation

Variable	Outer Loading	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Remarks
Transformational Leadership (X1)	0.728 – 0.923	0.750	0.886	0.923	Valid & Reliable
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.752 – 0.808	0.599	0.778	0.856	Valid & Reliable
Job Satisfaction (M)	0.759 – 0.903	0.700	0.914	0.933	Valid & Reliable
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.742 – 0.939	0.736	0.878	0.917	Valid & Reliable

(Source: Processed Data, 2025)

The results of the validity and reliability tests indicate that all constructs in this study meet the established criteria. The outer loading values for each indicator range from 0.728 to 0.923, indicating that all indicators are considered valid as they exceed the minimum threshold of 0.70. In addition, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for each variable are also above 0.50, namely transformational leadership (0.750), organizational culture (0.599), job satisfaction (0.700), and teacher performance (0.736), which indicates that the constructs are able to adequately explain the variance of their indicators. In terms of reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha values range from 0.778 to 0.914, and the Composite Reliability values range from 0.856 to 0.933, all of which exceed the minimum threshold of 0.70. Therefore, it can be concluded that the research instruments have a good level of internal consistency and are appropriate for further analysis.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The structural model evaluation (Structural Model/Inner Model) is conducted to assess the overall accuracy and predictive capability of the research model, which is constructed from several variables along with their respective indicators.

Table 3. Summary of Inner Model Evaluation

Model Testing	Indicator / Variable	Value	Criteria	Remarks
Multicollinearity (VIF)	All indicators	1.588 – 4.559	< 5.00	No multicollinearity
Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	Job Satisfaction (M)	0.794	> 0.50	Strong
	Teacher Performance (Y)	0.898	> 0.75	Very strong
Predictive Relevance (Q ²)	Job Satisfaction (M)	0.772	> 0	High predictive relevance
	Teacher Performance (Y)	0.738	> 0	High predictive relevance
Goodness of Fit (GoF)	Research model	0.767	> 0.36	Large fit

(Source: Processed Data, 2025)

The results of the structural model evaluation indicate that the research model meets the required criteria. The multicollinearity test shows that all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are below 5, indicating that there is no multicollinearity problem in the model. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination (R²) values indicate that the job satisfaction variable has an R² value of 0.794, meaning that 79.4% of the variation in job satisfaction can be explained by transformational leadership and organizational culture. Meanwhile, teacher performance has an R² value of 0.898, indicating that 89.8% of teacher performance is influenced by transformational leadership, organizational culture, and job satisfaction. The predictive relevance test (Q²) also shows positive values, namely 0.772 for job satisfaction and 0.738 for teacher performance, indicating that the model has high predictive capability. In addition, the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value is 0.767, which is higher than 0.36, suggesting that the research model has a very good level of fit in explaining the relationships among the studied variables.

Hypothesis Testing (Bootstrapping)

The bootstrapping test aims to determine the magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable, both directly and indirectly through the mediating variable. Furthermore, hypothesis testing is conducted to assess the relationships among constructs in the model and to determine whether they are consistent with the initial assumptions. The path coefficient and the level of significance (p-value) are used to evaluate the strength and direction of these relationships. A hypothesis is considered accepted if the p-value ≤ 0.05 and the t-statistic > 1.97. Conversely, if the p-value exceeds 0.05 and the t-statistic is less than 1.97, the hypothesis is rejected (Hair et al., 2022). The results of this stage serve as the basis for drawing conclusions regarding the causal relationships tested in the study.

Bootstrapping

1) Direct Hypothesis Testing

Table 4. Results of Direct Hypothesis Testing (Path Coefficients)

Hypothesis	Path Relationship	Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Values	Decision
H1	X1 → M	0.534	6.279	0.000	Accepted
H2	X2 → M	0.421	4.925	0.000	Accepted
H3	M → Y	0.810	7.751	0.000	Accepted
H4	X1 → Y	0.261	2.614	0.009	Accepted
H5	X2 → Y	-0.115	1.501	0.133	Rejected

(Source: Processed Data, 2025)

1. H1: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on job satisfaction ($T = 6.279, p = 0.000$).
2. H2: Organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction ($T = 4.925, p = 0.000$).
3. H3: Job satisfaction has a significant effect on teacher performance ($T = 7.751, p = 0.000$).
4. H4: Transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance ($T = 2.614, p = 0.009$).
5. H5: Organizational culture does not have a significant direct effect on teacher performance ($T = 1.501, p = 0.133$). The negative coefficient value (-0.115) and the non-significant result indicate that a positive organizational culture in this school does not necessarily improve teacher performance if it is not accompanied by job satisfaction

2) Indirect Hypothesis Testing (Mediation)

The mediation role of Job Satisfaction (M) was examined using the Variance Accounted For (VAF) approach.

Table 5. Summary of Mediation Test Results

Hypothesis	Mediation Path	Type of Mediation	Decision
H6	X1 → M → Y	Partial Mediation	Accepted
H7	X2 → M → Y	Full Mediation	Accepted

(Source: Processed Data, 2025)

1. Mediation of Job Satisfaction (M) in the Relationship between Transformational Leadership (X1) and Teacher Performance (Y)

The direct effect (X1 → Y) is 0.261, while the indirect effect (X1 → M → Y) is calculated as $0.534 \times 0.810 = 0.432$. Therefore, the total effect is $0.261 + 0.432 = 0.693$.

$$VAF = \frac{0,432}{0,693} \times 100\% = 62,3\%$$

Since the VAF value is 62.3% (within the range of 20%–80%), Job Satisfaction acts as a Partial Mediation in the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Teacher Performance. This means that leadership can influence performance both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction.

2. Mediation of Job Satisfaction (M) in the Relationship between Organizational Culture (X2) and Teacher Performance (Y)

It is found that the direct effect of Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance (X2 → Y) is not significant ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). However, the indirect effect (X2 → M → Y) is significant because both of its constituent paths (X2 → M and M → Y) are significant. In the SEM-PLS methodology, if the direct effect is not significant while the indirect effect is significant, this indicates the presence of Full Mediation. This means that organizational culture at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire can improve teacher performance only if the culture is able to create job satisfaction first.

Discussion

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Teachers’ Job Satisfaction

The results of this study indicate that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on teachers’ job satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. This finding suggests that the better the implementation of transformational leadership by the school principal, the higher the level of teachers’ job satisfaction in carrying out their professional duties. Transformational leadership demonstrated through role modeling, inspirational motivation, encouragement of creative thinking, and attention to individual needs can create positive work experiences for teachers. Teachers feel valued, supported, and receive clear direction in implementing the teaching and learning process. This condition fosters a sense of comfort and emotional attachment to the school, thereby increasing teachers’ job satisfaction. Theoretically, Bass and Riggio (2006) explain that transformational leadership can enhance subordinates’ job satisfaction through inspirational motivation, idealized influence, and individualized consideration toward the needs of organizational members. In the context of education, inspirational and supportive leadership can create a work environment that encourages teachers to feel appreciated and motivated in carrying out their

professional responsibilities. This finding is also supported by studies conducted by Mastur et al. (2022), Siahaan et al. (2023), and Rasidi et al. (2025), which found that transformational leadership plays an important role in increasing teachers' job satisfaction.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

The results of this study indicate that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on teachers' job satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. This finding suggests that a work environment characterized by clear values, norms, and work systems can enhance teachers' job satisfaction. An organizational culture that emphasizes cooperation, outcome orientation, and concern among organizational members creates a conducive and psychologically stable work environment. Teachers feel that they are part of a collective work system that supports one another in carrying out their professional responsibilities. This condition fosters a sense of security and comfort at work, thereby contributing to increased teacher job satisfaction. Theoretically, Schein (2010) states that organizational culture is a system of shared values that shapes how organizational members think, behave, and feel about their work. A positive organizational culture can foster a sense of belonging and enhance the psychological comfort of organizational members. Robbins and Judge (2017) also explain that a strong organizational culture can increase job satisfaction through the internalization of shared work values and norms.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Teacher Performance

The results of this study indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. This finding suggests that the higher the level of teachers' job satisfaction, the better the performance demonstrated in carrying out their professional duties. Job satisfaction creates positive feelings toward teachers' work, which in turn encourages intrinsic motivation to work more disciplinedly, responsibly, and actively in teamwork. Teachers who feel satisfied with their working conditions, relationships with colleagues, and support from leadership tend to demonstrate a higher level of commitment in carrying out teaching and learning activities. Theoretically, Robbins and Judge (2017) state that job satisfaction is an important predictor of individual behavior and performance within organizations. Individuals with high levels of job satisfaction tend to exhibit positive work attitudes, strong motivation, and better performance. This finding is also supported by studies conducted by Pratiwi (2021), Indayani (2021), and Astuti et al. (2025), which indicate that job satisfaction plays a strategic role in improving teacher performance.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Performance

The results of this study show that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. This finding indicates that the leadership behavior of the school principal is able to directly encourage improvements in teacher performance. A principal who is capable of providing a clear vision, work motivation, and attention to teachers' needs can create a collective work spirit that promotes improved performance quality. The leader's example in discipline and responsibility also becomes a model that teachers follow in carrying out their professional duties. Theoretically, Bass and Riggio (2006) explain that transformational leaders are able to enhance subordinates' performance through idealized influence and inspirational motivation, which encourage organizational members to go beyond personal interests in order to achieve organizational goals. In the context of education, visionary and inspirational school leadership can motivate teachers to work more professionally and focus on improving learning outcomes.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance

The results of this study indicate that organizational culture does not have a significant direct effect on teacher performance at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. This finding suggests that the presence of a positive organizational culture does not necessarily lead directly to improved teacher performance. Empirically, organizational culture tends to play a greater role in shaping work attitudes and perceptions rather than

directly influencing work behavior. Organizational values such as cooperation and outcome orientation can create a conducive work environment; however, their impact on performance often requires other psychological factors as mediating variables. This finding is consistent with organizational behavior theory, which states that organizational culture influences work behavior through the internalization of values and attitudes among organizational members (Schein, 2010). Robbins and Judge (2017) also explain that organizational culture often affects performance indirectly through psychological variables such as job satisfaction, motivation, and organizational commitment.

The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Teacher Performance

The results of this study indicate that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance. This finding suggests that the influence of leadership on performance occurs not only directly but also indirectly through increased teacher job satisfaction. Transformational leadership that provides motivation, individualized attention, and clear direction can enhance teachers' job satisfaction. Teachers who feel satisfied with their work are more likely to accept leadership guidance, demonstrate stronger commitment, and exhibit more disciplined and responsible work behavior. Theoretically, Robbins and Judge (2017) explain that job satisfaction functions as a psychological mechanism that mediates the influence of organizational factors on individual work behavior. Leadership that successfully enhances job satisfaction can strengthen organizational members' commitment and work motivation, which ultimately leads to improved performance.

The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Organizational Culture and Teacher Performance

The results of this study indicate that job satisfaction fully mediates the relationship between organizational culture and teacher performance. This finding suggests that organizational culture does not directly influence teacher performance but rather affects it through the enhancement of job satisfaction. A conducive organizational culture can foster a sense of togetherness, work comfort, and clarity of roles within the organization. These conditions increase teachers' job satisfaction, which in turn encourages them to work more disciplinedly, responsibly, and collaboratively. Theoretically, Schein (2010) states that organizational culture shapes work values and norms that influence individuals' attitudes and perceptions toward their work. When organizational values are able to create job satisfaction, these values can be more easily translated into productive work behavior. Robbins and Judge (2017) also explain that job satisfaction often serves as the primary mechanism linking organizational culture to individual performance within organizations.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that transformational leadership and organizational culture play important roles in shaping teachers' job satisfaction at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire. Transformational leadership is proven to have a positive effect on both job satisfaction and teacher performance, while organizational culture has a positive effect on job satisfaction but does not directly influence teacher performance. Job satisfaction emerges as a key factor that drives improvements in teacher performance and also functions as a mediating variable in the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational culture, and teacher performance. Job satisfaction partially mediates the effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance and fully mediates the effect of organizational culture on teacher performance. These findings indicate that improvements in teacher performance are not only influenced by organizational structural factors, but are also strongly determined by teachers' psychological conditions, as reflected in their level of job satisfaction.

Efforts to improve teacher performance at SMA Negeri 1 Nabire should be directed toward strengthening transformational leadership practices that are able to provide motivation, individualized attention, and support for teachers' professional development. Schools also need to reinforce an

organizational culture that promotes cooperation, open communication, and recognition of performance in order to sustainably enhance teachers' job satisfaction. Improving teachers' job satisfaction should become a primary concern through improvements in working conditions, workload balance, and a more equitable reward system. For the Education Office, the findings of this study may serve as a reference in designing policies related to school leadership development and the improvement of teacher welfare, particularly in 3T regions (Frontier, Remote, and Underdeveloped areas). Future research may develop the research model by incorporating additional variables such as work motivation, organizational commitment, or the work environment in order to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teacher performance.

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